

A Study on Students' Preference for Classroom Activities and Perceptions on Effectiveness of Those Activities in English Language Learning

Pale Mon

Lecturer, Department of English, University of Computer Studies, Thaton, Mon, Myanmar

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In Myanmar, teaching English to students aims to improve their language proficiency and equip them with useful learning processes and strategies to enhance the use of English for social and academic purposes. In order to be proficient in language learning, students must have fun and enjoyment activities in the classroom so that they participate in learning with enthusiasm and optimism for the outcomes.

It is very important for teachers to be able to teach and arouse students' interest in following the lesson in the classroom. For some students, learning English as a second language is one of the most difficult subjects they have learnt. Due to the difficulties in learning, English language can make students lose their interest easily. Interest is one of the strongest motivations for learning English. Motivation has long been identified as one of the main factors affecting English language learning (Gardner, 1985). Parsons, Hinson and Brown (2001) define motivation as an important component or factor in the learning process. Learning and motivation have the same importance in order to achieve something. Learning makes us gain new knowledge and skills and motivation pushes us or encourage us to go through the learning process (Wimolmas, 2013). Ellis (1997) stated that as teachers, we need to explore more fully the factors that are involved in motivating students to perform tasks well especially to participate enjoyably in classroom activities.

ABSTRACT

This paper explores students' preference for classroom activities and perceptions on effectiveness of those activities in learning English as a second language. The study followed both quantitative and qualitative research methodology. The study was conducted with 30 female and 12 male students from first year to fourth year and two of the teachers from English Language Department. The quantitative data were collected by questionnaires and they were structured the same 14 items that related to learning activities for the classroom. The data were evaluated by counting and converting the tallies into percentages. Qualitative method was chosen through face to face interview with 10 participants and 2 teachers to get in depth information about their teaching styles and students' preference for activities. The results showed that there were both similarities and differences among students' preferences for classroom activities and perceptions on effectiveness of those activities in language learning. Among the classroom activities they practiced, classroom conversations and group discussions were the most preference and effective one. Based on the findings obtained, conclusion and recommendations were given.

KEYWORDS: preference; effectiveness; classroom activities

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays technology, information and knowledge explosion have led to the increase of teaching and learning English as an international language.

FACTORS INFLUENCE PREFERENCE FOR LEARNING ACTIVITIES

Many factors influence preference for learning activities in the language classroom; for example, learning and teaching styles, motivation, students' perception of usefulness or importance, classroom environment, personality, or language level. At times, teachers need to manage activities based on the possibilities available within their particular context.

Activities might have positive and negative consequences. If teachers are able to make use of appropriate activities in the classroom, these activities could be the mediator to increase students' motivation and to decrease their anxiety. On the contrary, they might also bring consequences such as demotivation, increasing anxiety, boredom, absenteeism, or even dropping out of class. Nikolov (2009) showed that when activities were not motivating for students, it had a negative effect on learners' motivation. Renninger (2009) explains that it is possible for students to develop and deepen an interest in a topic over time, and that a person's environment (classroom, teachers, peers, texts, activities, etc.) contributes to this interest.

In general, activities play an important role in the process of learning in the classroom. However, it is necessary to define the term activity. Nunan (1991) defines the term "activities"

as the elements of the task that specifies what the students will actually perform with the input; for instance, listening to recordings, writing a sentence, answering questions, etc. Coughlan and Duff (1994) define activity as the behavior that actually takes place when an individual performs a task. Similarly, Brown (2000) defines activity as “a reasonably unified set of student behaviors, limited in time, preceded by some direction from the teacher with a particular objective” (p. 159). The literature (e.g., Moore, 2001; Nunan, 1991) explains that it is important to take into consideration students’ opinions for the selection of the activities and that a good selection of classroom activities engages students, facilitates learning, gives the teacher and students immediate feedback, and raises interests and motivation.

TEACHING STYLES AND TEACHERS’ BELIEVES IN CHOOSING ACTIVITIES FOR THE CLASSROOM

The way teachers choose, adapt, and deliver classroom activities reflects their teaching styles and their methods or approaches to teach (e.g., audio-lingual, direct method, grammar translation, communicative approach, etc.). Sometimes teachers are not aware of the methods they use; consequently, choosing activities for the classroom much depends on their preference or the way they know how to transmit information, in other words, their teaching style.

Fan and Ye (2007) defined teaching style as the unique way teachers solve problems, conduct tasks, and make decisions in their teaching. Similarly, Ghanizadeh and Jahedizadeh (2015) posit that “teaching style refers to all of teaching techniques, activities and approaches that a teacher employs in teaching a certain subject in the classroom” (p. 2). Thus, teachers perceive teaching in different ways and try to accommodate their style to learner’s needs in order to facilitate learning. Rao (2002) argues that matching styles effectively can only be achieved when teachers are aware of students’ needs, capacities, potentials, and learning style preferences. The way a teacher approaches teaching can be both dangerous and beneficial for learning if their teaching differs from students’ learning style. Felder and Spurlin (2005) claim that when there are mismatches, students might experience a feeling of boredom and may become inattentive, discouraged, demotivated about the class, or even with themselves, and, consequently, they may abandon the class.

It is important to consider that in order to match teaching and learning styles, teachers need to deal with conditions that could make it difficult such as having large classes. They prefer some classroom activities over others because of their perception of the usefulness, enjoyment, or motivational effect activities have on students.

INFLUENCE OF ACTIVITIES IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

Activities used in the classroom are important to learning in many ways. In compulsory classes, these factors might influence the decision of willingly attending class. The importance of knowing the activities that students like to have or do in the classroom will bring about students’ enjoyment within the classroom environment, thus leading to attentive participation. Zhu (2012) found that interesting activities for students such as classroom games, for instance, guessing games, picture games, miming, debates, jigsaw activities, and role plays can improve students’ communicative ability. In the same vein, Chanseawrassamee

(2012) demonstrated that adult learners could have positive attitudes towards appealing activities. In the same way, Dörnyei and Csizer (1998) proposed a list of activities which stimulate students’ interests as one important factor for motivating language learners. Including a wide variety of activities and tasks in the classroom that learners prefer can create a more interactive environment in which students will be more willing to participate. In this sense, both teachers and students can enjoy the learning experience.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research components. In order to explore students’ preferences and enjoyment for classroom activities, questionnaires with a Likert scale were given out to the students to collect numerical data. After having analysed the data obtained from the questionnaires, 10 participants and 2 teachers were asked to elaborate on some of their answers in the interview to gain more in depth information regarding this inquire. In the language proficiency class, all students did the activities use of the blending methods by the author instructions and it focused on a learner-centered approach to facilitate the language learning process.

Research Questions

The research project was guided by the following two research questions:

1. What are the students’ preferences and enjoyment for classroom activities?
2. Are the classroom activities they prefer effective for their language learning?

Participants

Participants of this study were teachers and students of University of Computer Studies (Thaton) (UCST). The study was conducted with 30 female and 12 male students from first year to fourth year and the participants’ age ranged from 18-22 years. They all were attending the English Language Proficiency class at UCST in order to improve their English language skills. It was opened after finishing the final exam in 2018 and took ten hours per week for two months. Two of the teachers from English Language Department were also participated in interview to support the survey and to give more information about learning activities they use in the class and ways of arousing students’ interest in learning English.

Instruments

Questionnaires were used to gather data about students’ preference for activities and their effectiveness that they practiced in class. They were structured the same 14 items that related to learning activities for the classroom based on Dörnyei’s (2002) observations and Littlewood’s (2010) research article. The answers obtained from the Likert scale survey questions were evaluated by counting and converting the tallies into percentages. The data were presented in a table. Presenting the quantitative data in a table that displays frequency and percentage distribution of the numerical data makes it more easily comprehensible and additionally, enables one to see the differences among the various groups of values more quickly (Levine & Stephan, 2010). Furthermore, the data collected using interview were qualitatively analyzed. Finally, based on the findings obtained, conclusion and recommendations were given.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary aims of this research were to identify students' preferences for activities and those were effective and enjoyable for their learning.

In order to support students' preference of learning activities, the two teachers expressed their teaching styles and activities they used in the classroom. Teacher A has more than ten years teaching experiences and teacher B has nearly 7 years. Teacher A stated that she used both traditional and communicative language teaching methods in her language teaching. She brought into role-plays, picture descriptions, and games activities in pairs and group work in the class. In addition, she prepared extra printed colourful materials such as pictures, display cards, photos and posters to support her teaching. Furthermore, she also mentioned that those activities used in the class could attract students' attention and interest in following the lesson and most students preferred and enjoyed them. However, she pointed out that some students felt shy and anxiety to communicate to other students while doing activities. When they spoke out, they had no words to say. They were lack in vocabulary to use and knowledge. On the other hand, the class time period was not sufficient to practice more activities in class to be competence. For these reasons, they did not enjoy to participate in class.

Concerning the teacher B's views, she showed authentic videos and popular songs to improve students' listening skill in her teaching and most of them liked listening to songs. She claimed that she rarely used communicative activities in the class because she thought managing to use activities took too much time. Due to exam oriented testing system, she needed to end her lectures on time. Thus, she mostly taught the students with the traditional methods. She complained that students were not interested in grammar exercises when she used traditional methods but they favoured to play games for that exercises. She stated that they felt bored and disliked learning English. They thought English is difficult subject.

As above mentioned, students' preferences activities, the two teachers' teaching styles and perceptions were different. Some teaching methods and use of activities could not stimulate their inner motivation and enhance the interest of the class. The use of inappropriate learning methods could fail active and fun learning atmosphere so it is possible that the achievement of learning goals is unsuccessful.

Several research studies have shown that teacher and student perceptions regarding teaching strategies and learning activities are not always in accordance with each other (e.g. Block, 1994; Barkhuizen, 1998; Nunan, 1986). Thus, by examining the preferences of students, inferences can be made for the implementation of instructional methods and learning activities in English language classes in order to facilitate and support the students' language learning.

Results indicated that students favored activities in which they practiced by using innovative teaching methods in the language proficiency class. From the results shown in Table 1, the highest preferences for activities was classroom conversations and group discussions (95.23%, n=40). Concerning those activities, interviewee A expressed his surprise that he could improve his fluency and also feel more

confident every time he had the chance to speak and could learn both from the teacher and the other students. In addition, he could have the opportunity to increase his vocabulary.

Besides of this, interviewee B also mentioned that he had so much fun because the conversation class was interactive and ludic as well. Moreover he said that group discussions helped him to explore a diversity of perspectives. He could be awareness of and tolerance for ambiguity or complexity to each other and recognize and investigate assumptions within his group. He had respectful listening and developed habits of collaborative learning. He had never felt bored while doing the activity.

Therefore, we must provide an environment where students are willing to engage in conversations that allow them to communicate their ideas. Teachers' awareness of students' knowledge can more thoroughly support meaningful learning and critical thinking (Carpenter, et al., 2004).

Providing students with numerous opportunities to contribute to thought-provoking discussions surrounding content increases student participation and willingness to present their ideas related to topics of instruction. Moreover, as teachers improve their capacity for using higher-order questions to guide student discourse, they also are able to more readily perceive student misconceptions and redirect students with questions that allow them to revisit their thinking, dialogue with their peers, and choose a different approach or conclusion (Johnson, et al., 2013).

Barely displaying a difference to the previous percentage, in the second highest preference, (76.19%, n=32) of participants thought they had the same enjoyment in playing games, singing and listening to songs, oral presentations, pronunciation practice and small group work. 5 out of 10 interviewees considered that playing games helped them to feel more confident to develop their speaking and English in general. The games could help them to express themselves and of course to understand much more because with games was funnier and when they played they learned to speak by learning vocabulary. They integrated each other by thinking in the game, they forgot the shyness and they paid more attention in class. Interviewee C and D demonstrated a positive attitude. By playing games they got to enjoy what they are doing. So teaching something through that game, that's a really good process of teaching a student.

The reason for liking singing and listening to songs was the fact that songs are one method for achieving a weak affective filter and promoting language learning. With the affective filter weak, Saricoban and Metin (2000) have found that songs can develop the four skill areas of reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Lo and Li (1998) offer similar suggestions, writing that songs provide a break from classroom routine, and that learning English through songs develops a non-threatening classroom atmosphere in which the four language skills can be enhanced. Students believed that songs could provide enjoyment and develop language skills.

Interviewee E' standpoint was in accordance with this statement. After listening to the song, he thought that he could create his own present progressive sentences based

upon his own interest. Students could create their own lyrics following the same tune as the song. Using songs can prepare students for the genuine language they will be faced with. If students are exposed to songs which they enjoy, more learning is likely to occur since they may seek out the music outside of the classroom.

Results also indicated that students thought practicing pronunciation was one of the fun activities. When practicing pronouncing technique and special points such as features of stress, rhythm, intonation, linking syllables, ellipsis, among others, the some interviewees were confident on learning the right pronunciation patterns, while more than half of respondents expressed the belief that they could come close to the native English speakers once they did their best in pronunciation lessons. Moreover, interviewee F pointed out that she and her colleagues found great delight in practicing pronunciation when they tried to pronounce the words clearly that made them fun.

Engaging in the interactive exercises like dialogues, paragraph readings, short presentations, picture descriptions and interview exercises helped the students not only command improved pronunciation patterns but also have more confidence in English speaking. In addition, as the students engaged in the interactive activities, most of them could pin-point their problems themselves even before the facilitators corrected them. Hence this was an equally effective technique for the students to have better pronunciation patterns.

In regard to small group work, the participants displayed their views. Interviewee B and E said that working and discussing in groups is “the best teaching technique a teacher can have”, because once they were in a group, they had to be active; they needed to put in; they input to be a part of the group and to be an active member. They had to do some critical thinking and the best learning thing for a student is to have group sessions or probably small group work, conversations and everything.

The concept of students working in groups also promotes a setting where collaboration and cooperation are valued and produce better results, teaching the students valuable life-long skills that are important in the professional workplace. They hold one another responsible and accountable. Students know how to plan more effectively and manage their time.

Concerning the oral presentations, Interviewees G, H and I stated that this activity made them more creative to use any source and information from web or books. By presentation, the teacher gave them chance to speak up, learned how to speak up in front of many people and build self-confidence to speak in English. It made them more creative, active, and developed their knowledge. In addition, they had more friendship and fascinating discussion time to share their ideas. They also felt that oral presentation could make them become more independent in learning as they read and understand the material by themselves before they could ask for help from the other members of the group, from their classmates and the lecturer. Besides, they could put their English into practice, mostly orally and partly in writing, in interactional communication with their classmates and lecturer. Oral presentations allow students the opportunity to teach one another instead of learning from the lecturer.

Ranking third role plays was preferred with approximately (71.42%, n=30). Interviewees A, E and J also considered that role-play enhanced their learning and they felt very comfortable with the role playing approach. In addition, interviewee D pointed out that incorporating role-play into a class did not only help in language learning, but was also beneficial for his studies in general. He believed that it helped him to get a better understanding of various topics and theories. Jose and King (2012) found that role play brings situations from real life into the classroom. The use of role play method would be more interesting and fun for students that would affect both the activities of learners in the learning activities. Students are required to be actively involved in the learning activities, while the role of teachers as facilitators.

The fourth ranking for activities students’ choice was usage of visual material (66.66%, n=28). Relating to it, Interviewee F supposed that when he looked at images, he was hastening the responses of his brain. Unlike in traditional learning when all they get to see was black and white text, visual learning through images helped them retain the information for a longer time. Then his mind would be able to recapitulate a picture faster when compared to simple text. Hence, it is through movies and videos that he could process information in a jiffy and store it in his mind for immediate retrieval.

In line with the famous maxim “A picture is worth a thousand words”, an image has a profound impact on the brain of a student. If a student is learning through educational videos, he will be using a large portion of his/her mental power. This is because of the fact that a major part of student’s brain is devoted exclusively to process visual information. Using picture is an effort to help students to understand and comprehend something clearly and easily. Visual learning goes a long way in engaging students with their study topics, ultimately improving their concentration levels. Due to the strength of visual learning, topics are not only understood easily and quickly but also favor an effective application of assimilated visual content. Visual learning will not only educate students with subject knowledge but will also pave the way for holistic growth which surfaces in the form of improved concentration and creativity.

In addition, (57.14%, n=24) of participants liked vocabulary list and more teacher explanations activities in learning at the fifth rank. All of the interviewees had positive perception about vocabulary learning. Vocabulary learning helped them in their academic study, which means it helps them to read, speak, write, and listen effectively. It also helped them in their network study to share information among themselves clearly. The students also said that vocabulary could not be mastered overnight rather it needs ceaseless practice and critical thinking. In general, without vocabulary knowledge it is unthinkable to be successful student. More than half of participants perceived vocabulary as one of the important skills for their academic study. It helped them in developing their English language skills like reading, speaking, writing, listening and knowledge of grammar. Wong (2009) demonstrated that vocabulary learning is also achieved through connections via dual channels of speaking and writing. Shaking out the words and spelling the words, she says, brings “awareness to the letters in the word and connection between the spoken words onto written text”

(Wong, 2009, p. 9). To improve the quality of English teaching and learning, it is suggested that the English teacher had to create the suitable technique in improving the students' motivation in learning English vocabulary.

Moreover, teacher explanations were seen in a favorable light, because its purpose was to facilitate the learning process and ultimately make it easier for the students. Some interviewees claimed that they confused some questions when they read them and they could understand the processes to do the task if the teacher explained to them. Another interviewee described the benefits of teacher explanations in the following way: the teacher knows the stuff. The teacher has gone through, realizes the difficulties that the students would have in terms of understanding what they are trying to explain. So, really, they make it much easier. They walk the students around the problems that students would have if they didn't have the teacher. Since it is inevitable that learners will face difficulties and problems during their learning process, the teacher's expertise and awareness in regard to potential struggles are seen as an enormous and valuable support for the learner.

Furthermore, participants enjoyed translation exercises (52.38%, n=22) as the sixth rank. One interviewee expressed her views on translation exercises during our interviews. Interviewee G was of the opinion that, in terms of speaking, translation exercises were not effective at all. She favored written translation due to several different reasons. She pointed out that the good thing of translation is that it really helped her to dissect the sentences and analyze the sentence, because she fascinated to accurately translate technical papers. So in terms of learning the sentence structure, she thought it was really helpful, and at the same time it helped her write essay, because she knew the structure of the sentence.

Conversely, the least preferences activities of students were grammar exercises, usage of real life materials and error corrections by the teacher (each 47.61%, n=20) respectively.

Interviewee D identified the reason for liking error corrections by the teacher was the fact that one would get feedback on their frequently made mistakes at a timely manner, and therefore, could work specifically on those to improve one's skills.

Despite the fact that grammar exercises were apparently used quite often in their former English classes, some participants indicated that they were the least preference activities. Even though results did not favor grammar activities in its entirety, grammar plays an important role in teaching amongst the most frequently used activities. Commonly, learners believe that in order to be able to be proficient in English, it is necessary to learn the correct use of grammar in spite of what the communicative approaches suggest. Schulz's (1996) study revealed that students believed that in order to master a language, it was necessary to study grammar. Similarly, Richards and Rodgers (2001) suggest that explicit grammar teaching is beneficial to students regardless of the existing movement toward a communicative approach to English language teaching. Thus, teachers who aim at communication might see grammar as not necessary whereas students would find it useful in their learning. While teachers seem to notice the importance of improving students' communicative competence, they also aim at accuracy for grammatical competence.

Although visual and real life material were one of the least preference of students, they, especially TV programs, were said to provide opportunities to learn vocabulary, everyday expressions and pronunciation and additionally, offer authentic learning experiences. One interviewee claimed that, having real life experiences or that exercises actually helped students to connect with his own life or he had experienced those things, so he could connect well to it and that's why he got more interested into learning about that thing and that's what motivates him in a way to learn more deeply into it. However, as already mentioned, most students enjoyed the activities, few of them dislike translation exercises, usage of real life materials, vocabulary lists and playing games [each 2.38% (n=1)].

Table 1. Students' Preference of the highest to the lowest activities

Rank	Item No.	Learning Activity	N	%
1.	5	Classroom conversations and Group discussions	40	95.23
2.	6	Small group work	32	76.19
2.	10	Playing Games	32	76.19
2.	3	Pronunciation practice	32	76.19
2.	4	Singing and listening to songs	32	76.19
2.	14	Oral presentations	32	76.19
3.	7	Role-plays	30	71.42
4.	12	Use of visual material (e.g. pictures, movies)	28	66.66
5.	9	Vocabulary lists	24	57.14
5.	13	More Teacher explanation	24	57.14
6.	2	Translation exercises	22	52.38
7.	11	Error corrections by the teacher	20	47.61
7.	8	Use of real life material (TV, radio shows, newspaper, etc.)	20	47.61
7.	1	Grammar exercises	20	47.61

In regard to the results from the Table 2, the ranking of the learning activities and instructional methods that the students' perceived as most effective slightly differed from the ones that were popular among them, but the chosen items were the same. The second question on the questionnaire asked the participants to evaluate 14 learning and teaching strategies by using a Likert scale, which was divided into categories of very effective, effective, somewhat effective, somewhat ineffective, and ineffective. When looking solely on the numbers of the "very effective" category, classroom conversations and group discussions ranked in first place with (95.23%, n=40) indicating that it is at most effective. Both small group work and pronunciation practice were in second place (each 90.47%, n=38); and third place was taken by role plays (85.71%, n=36). Both oral presentations and grammar exercises ranked in fourth place with (each 80.95%, n=34), and both singing and listening to songs and error corrections by the teacher came in fifth place (each 76.19%, n=32).

Despite the fact that grammar exercises were apparently described one of the least preference activities for participants, it came the fourth effective one. It was with some surprise that classroom conversations and group discussions; singing and listening to songs; use of real life material and use of visual material activities were both the same favour and effectiveness ones in both categories. Playing games, which had initially been perceived as a rather very enjoyment method (76.19%, n=32), now ranked only ninth (52.38%, n=22). Nevertheless, some participants felt that playing games was a good way to motivate students because it did not necessarily make them feel like they were explicitly learning. One interviewee suggested that since younger children learned mostly through play, it should continue throughout one's life. Furthermore, another one claimed that if the teacher was able to develop a meaningful game for his or her students, then it would "attract students and make them interested into what he's trying to say or what he's teaching, so it's definitely effective and helpful for student

In general, the activities students preferred and their effectiveness for the participants are not very mismatch. Students may favor activities based on a wider range of reasons, for instance, activities in which they feel comfortable, pleased, entertained, interested, or simply because they liked it. As seen previously, there are some factors that can be accounted for the activities learners prefer in the classroom: teaching and learning styles, students' needs for studying the language, students' lack of language, the classroom environment, students' motivation, time allocated for the class, and even their own literacy in their native language.

Table2. Students' Preference of the activities in terms of Preference ranking (Enjoyment) and Effectiveness

Learning Activity		Preference Ranking (Enjoyment)	Effectiveness
1.	Grammar exercises	47.61%	80.95%
2.	Translation exercises	52.38%	57.14%
3.	Pronunciation practice	76.19%	90.47%
4.	Singing and listening to songs	76.19%	76.19%
5.	Classroom conversations and Group discussions	95.23%	95.23%
6.	Small group work.	76.19%	90.47%
7.	Role-plays	71.42%	85.71%
8.	Use of real life material (TV, radio shows, newspaper, etc.)	47.61%	47.61%
9.	Vocabulary lists	57.14%	71.42%
10.	Playing Games	76.19%	52.38%
11.	Error corrections by the teacher	47.61%	76.19%
12.	Use of visual material (e.g. pictures, movies)	66.66%	66.66%
13.	More Teacher explanation	57.14%	71.42%
14.	Oral presentations	76.19%	80.95%

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study explored students' preference for and effectiveness of classroom activities in English language learning. Since it was a small case study, it aims to find the activities students prefer and their opinions on those activities are effective in the second language learning through practice.

Since every learner is unique and perceives activities differently, many factors can be attributed to their preference for activities; for example, students' enjoyment when performing the activity, the degree of anxiety that the activity provokes, the perception of usefulness it has in their learning, etc. Ideally, teachers should include activities that learners enjoy doing and which benefits their learning but this does not always happen (Samperio,2017). Thus, a careful selection of activities that can involve learning and enjoyment is not very easy; however, there can be a

negotiation between actors in the inclusion of activities in the classroom. Both teachers and students can come to agreements on what should be included in the classroom. Teachers can always opt for a negotiation with students by openly asking students the type of activities they prefer having in class. The teachers' role is to choose the activities that can please both parties, then their expectations for activities can be fulfilled. This would increase motivation and help in developing an enjoyable environment.

According to Anil (2017), practical knowledge of learning a language is an experimental approach for second language learners. Such learners should experiment their knowledge by communicating with others confidently. Their errors can be rectified or pruned through this practice. Teachers should develop students' confidence, independence, interest, and aid them to realize that their first language knowledge repository would be helpful to learn the second language

confidently. Teachers should discover activities and tasks that are filled with edutainment. Introducing various tasks would help learners to understand the use of language in real-life situations by engaging them in doing many activities in the classroom.

Teachers should think of new and varied activities to empower students to face many real challenges in their future life. Such activities make students to think and react proactively, innovatively and confidently. Performing the activities in the classroom will make students to have authorship over themselves and develop good rapport with teachers and fellow students. Learners' autonomy is an appreciable act and teachers should understand their students' strength and weakness in learning English as a language rather than a subject. Teachers should think of practical activities that should be filled with humor and creativity (Allwright, 1984). Creativity helps learners to use language relevantly. Teacher should prepare the materials for students that could be performed as practical activities in the classroom. Activities can mould students to be a thinker, analyzer, judge, and evaluator and aid them to fit in according to the situation. Using innovative methodologies in teaching English in the classroom will pave a positive way to students to learn the language meaningfully. Students will understand the significance of learning English as a second language without any fear which will help them to equip with the power of confidence and achievement. It is hope that a further research study in this area will be conducted widely in the future.

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APPENDICES

Appendix: I

Questionnaire I

Directions: Please indicate which of the following category applies best for each statement by placing an “X” in the appropriate column.

Which of these activities did you find to be enjoyable?

Learning Activity		Like	Neutral	Dislike
1.	Grammar exercises			
2.	Translation exercises			
3.	Pronunciation practice			
4.	Singing and listening to songs			
5.	Classroom conversations and Group discussions			
6.	Small group work.			
7.	Role-plays			
8.	Use of real life material (TV, radio shows, newspaper, etc.)			
9.	Vocabulary lists			
10.	Playing Games			
11.	Error corrections by the teacher			
12.	Use of visual material (e.g. pictures, movies)			
13.	More Teacher explanation			
14.	Oral presentations			

Questionnaire II

Directions: Please indicate which of the following category applies best for each statement by placing an “X” in the appropriate column.

Which of these activities did you find effective for your studies?

Learning Activity		Very effective	Effective	Somewhat effective	Somewhat ineffective	Ineffective
1.	Grammar exercises					
2.	Translation exercises					
3.	Pronunciation practice					
4.	Singing and listening to songs					
5.	Classroom conversations and Group discussions					
6.	Small group work.					
7.	Role-plays					
8.	Use of real life material (TV, radio shows, newspaper, etc.)					
9.	Vocabulary lists					
10.	Playing Games					
11.	Error corrections by the teacher					
12.	Use of visual material (e.g. pictures, movies)					
13.	More Teacher explanation					
14.	Oral presentations					

